

SOFTWARE CUSTOMIZATION OF THE BODY MOVEMENT SUPPORT AND ASSISTANCE SYSTEM

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Introduction: Daily physical activity plays a fundamental role in the well-being and health status of people, including those with some degree of dependence. Therefore, it becomes essential to maintain beneficial physical and emotional conditions. Adequate physical activity must be sought to maintain muscle strength, a wide range of joint movements, reeducate them, provide them with sleep, coordination, posture correction, increase proprioception, general physical exercise, muscle stretching, muscle relaxation, breathing exercises, among others.

Lack of physical activity generates changes in the state of health, limitations in functional capacity, and disability. This is manifested from a social and biological point of view, directly influencing the quality of life. In view of these facts, it is essential to carry out activities, programs, and systematic and frequent exercises for basic actions to tolerate everyday situations on the part of those who take care of these people. It is also important to establish appropriate guidelines, all aimed at attaining better biological and social functioning and greater involvement in everyday life, always taking into account individual characteristics.

Today, with the increasing severity of work and aging of the population, the care industry is also being pressed due to a decrease in the number of housewives, and the demand for care robots and related systems is increasing. In the research field of the system used in the care industry, systems that use sensors and motion capture to acquire user behavior and planning algorithms that generate user support and assistance motions are actively being researched. However, there are not many user support and assistance systems that will be put to practical use. First, these systems are often not diversified. Second, many of these systems cannot interact with people. Third, there is little consideration for dealing with problems when multiple systems with different functions are used. To address these problems, we proposed the whole-body support and assistance system for conducting user support and assistance based on the body support and assistance request given to activation by the user, which combines new elements as an environment for humans.

The rapid advancements in technology have revolutionized various aspects of our lives, and one such area that has witnessed significant growth is assistive technology. The Body Movement Support and Assistance System, designed to aid individuals with physical disabilities, has undergone a paradigm shift with the incorporation of software customization. This innovative approach has empowered individuals with impaired mobility to regain control over their daily lives, thereby enhancing their overall quality of life. The Body Movement Support and Assistance System, an amalgamation of sensors, actuators, and control systems, is designed to provide support and assistance to individuals with physical disabilities. This system, consisting of wearable devices, exoskeletons, and prosthetics, enables individuals to

perform daily tasks with increased ease and independence. However, the initial generic design of these systems often failed to cater to the unique needs of each individual, resulting in suboptimal performance and user dissatisfaction. It is here that software customization plays a pivotal role in bridging the gap between the system's capabilities and the user's requirements. Software customization of the Body Movement Support and Assistance System involves the tailoring of software algorithms to accommodate the specific needs and preferences of each individual user. This process begins with a comprehensive assessment of the user's physical abilities, mobility, and daily requirements. The gathered data is then used to develop a personalized software model that optimizes the system's performance, ensuring seamless interaction between the user and the assistive technology. One of the primary benefits of software customization is the enhancement of user experience. By adapting the system to an individual's unique characteristics, users can effortlessly interact with the assistive technology, minimizing frustration and discomfort. For instance, a user with paralysis may require a customized software model that adjusts the sensitivity of the wearable device to accommodate their limited mobility. This tailored approach enables users to regain control over their bodies, thereby improving their overall confidence and independence.

Furthermore, software customization facilitates the optimization of the system's performance, resulting in improved accuracy and efficiency. By incorporating machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence, the system can learn the user's habits and preferences, adapting to their needs over time. This self-learning capability enables the system to anticipate the user's intentions, providing proactive support and assistance. For example, a customized software model can predict a user's intention to stand up from a seated position, providing the necessary support and stabilization to ensure safe and effortless movement. In addition to enhancing user experience and system performance, software customization also plays a crucial role in promoting health and wellness. By providing users with real-time feedback and analytics, the system enables them to monitor their progress, set goals, and track their achievements. This data-driven approach empowers users to take proactive control over their health and wellness, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility. The implications of software customization extend beyond the realm of assistive technology, as it has far-reaching consequences for the healthcare industry as a whole. The development of personalized software models has paved the way for predictive analytics, enabling healthcare professionals to identify trends and patterns in patient data. This data-driven approach enables healthcare professionals to provide targeted interventions, reducing healthcare costs, and improving patient outcomes.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, software customization of the Body Movement Support and Assistance System has revolutionized the field of assistive technology, providing individuals with physical disabilities with a newfound sense of independence and control over their lives. By tailoring software algorithms to cater to the unique needs and preferences of each individual, this approach has enhanced user experience, optimized system performance, and promoted health and wellness. As technology continues to evolve, the potential for software customization to transform the lives of individuals with physical disabilities is vast, and its impact will undoubtedly be felt across the healthcare industry as a whole.

References:

1. Anybody Technology A/S. Anybody Modeling System. [1.3.0]. 2004. Aalborg (Denmark).
2. Christensen's., Siebert., Dalsgaard., de Seem., Rasmussen., and Paul. (2003) Human seat modeling using inverse dynamic Musculo-skeletal models. Digital Human Modeling for Design and Engineering, Society of Automotive Engineers, Montreal, Canada.
3. Madeleine., Jorgensen., Sogaard,K., Arendt-Nielsen,L., and Sjogaard,G. (2002) Development of muscle fatigue as assessed by electromyography and mechanomyography during continuous and intermittent low-force contractions: effects of the feedback mode. Burj Appl Physio 87, 28-37.
4. Rasmussen,J. and Christensen,S.T. (2005) Musculoskeletal modeling of egress with the Anybody Modeling System. Digital Human Modeling for Design and Engineering, Society of Automotive Engineers, Iowa City, USA.
5. Reinecke's., Hazarder., and Coleman,K. (1994) Continuous passive motion in seating: a new strategy against low back pain. J Spinal Discord. 7, 29-35

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